

DETERMINING THE INTERESTS AND PARTICIPATION LEVELS OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS TO SPORTIVE RECREATION ACTIVITIES

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Abstract:

Reduction of working hours and increase of the spare time with technological development provided people to stay the level of education and income. Therefore, inadequate physical activity based on the industry has become one of the biggest problems of people and societies in our day. As a result of them the demand of recreational activities has increased. It is important for our future to educate young people about these issues. This study which is conducted for participation of college students to sportive recreation activities and determining their interests has been done with the aim of contribution to our future. Target population of study is 245 students (121 girls and 129 boys) that are randomly chosen and studying in Academy of Kırkpınar Physical Education and Sports and the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences in Trakya University. The data of the research were collected as a survey. The obtained data were analyzed on SPSS 15 program. Chi-square test, frequency and crosstabs analyses were used. The proportion of the students who participated the research was %48 of girl and %52 of boy. There were 126 participants from Kırkpınar College of Physical Education and Sports and 119 participants from Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences. In total, 300 surveys were used for this research. 245 of them were taken under review. Most of the students take part in the activities for their health and generally they prefer being with their groups of friends.

Keywords: leisure, recreation, sportive recreation, sport, university

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1. Introduction

Technological development made societies economically more proper and this has caused the machines replace time that people have to spare for work. By this means, recreative activities have gained more importance today in order to people spend time left over work and physical needs relaxing and joyful.

Social and cultural life changed with the Industrial Revolution revealed the term "leisure time." During this leisure time, the people who want to spend the time effectively need to make their wants and programs properly.

While Godbey defines leisure time as living in relative freedom from the external compulsive forces of one's culture and physical environment (Godbey, 1999:12). Wichasin (2007:21) defines it as freedom from constraint, opportunity to choose, time left over work, free time after obligatory social duties have been met.

Recuperating and sustaining body and spiritual well-being, where human intensive workload is endangered or adversely affected by routinely lifestyle or adverse environmental effects can also provide pleasure and harmfulness, personal satisfaction, independent and unconnected free time remaining at the time reserved for work and compulsory needs, voluntary and voluntary individual or group activities (Karaküçük, 1995).

Sport has two kinds of activities as a recreation activity. First of them is passive participation as a spectator and second one is active participation by having a part in it. Whereas watching a contest or training of any branch of sports is passive recreative participation, watching the same contest or training at home with television is passive recreative activity. However, there are some differences between them like the inequality of place, excitement and reaction.

Passive recreative activity can change according to apprehension and habits. When it is considered to people gravitate to some of the branches and they tend to be player of them although they were just spectators before, it is clear that transition from passive participation to activity is inspirer.

Today, every student spending most of their time in class, laboratories or on desk need to participate recreative activities. Therefore, the universities' activity programs have to create opportunities for recreation and rest so that student can get over the stress of modern life and school studies. The necessary effort, designing and programming should be done for this.

2. Material and Methods

This is a scanning study. The whole literature about the topic was scanned and former studies in this area were analyzed. In the light of these information, Determining The Level of Participation and Interest of College Students to Sportive Recreation Activities Target population of study is 5,982 students studying at Academy of Kırkpınar Physical Education and Sports and the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences in Trakya University between 2015-2015. The sample group of research is 126 persons studying at Academy of Kırkpınar Physical Education and Sports, 119 persons from Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences. The study is oriented by assessment and conducted with determining the extent and method, scanning the literature, using the survey and evaluating the data.

The data obtained were analyzed with the SPSS 15.0 programmes. Frequency tables, percentage places, and chi square test were carried out in statistical analyzes. At the beginning of the research, the level of relevance was determined as 0,05 and the results were in computer environment.

3. Results and Discussion

These results were obtained from the information collected in research.

Table 1: Demographic Information

Gender	N	%
Female	117	47,8
Male	128	52,2
Total	245	100,0
Age Range		
18-20	105	42,9
21-23	102	41,6
24-26	33	13,5
27-29	3	1,2
30 and more	2	0,8
Total	245	100,0
Department		
Academy of Kırkpınar Physical Education and Sports	146	51,4
Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences	119	48,6
Total	245	100,0
Interested in Sport During Childhood		
Yes	196	80,0
No	49	20,0
Total	245	100,0

117 female students in research constitute of the %47,8. 128 male students constitute of the %52,2 and there are 245 students in total. It is a fact that 105 of the students between 18-20 ages constitute of %42,9 and 102 of them between 21-23 ages constitute of %41,6. The research's area does not include classroom. Therefore, it is considered that results are normal when regarding the students is chosen randomly and possibility of participation from each classroom. While %51,4 of the students are studying at Academy of Kırkpınar Physical Education and Sports, %48,6 of them are studying at Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences. Whereas %80 of the students interested in sports during their childhoods answer yes, rest of them answer no. Indeed, most of the students interested in sports during their childhoods.

Table 2: The chi-square results between the state of playing sport of students and their mothers

The state of playing sports of students			The state of playing sports of mothers			Total
			Yes	No	Sometimes	
			Yes	N	18	
	%	8,5	62,0	29,6	100,0	
No	N	0	24	8	32	
	%	,0	75,0	25,0	100,0	
Total	N	18	156	71	245	
	%	7,3	63,7	29,0	100,0	

P<0,05

Chi-Square	Value	SD	Significance
Pearson	3,647	2	,161
Likelihood Ratio	5,956	2	,051
Linear-by-linear Association	,131	1	,717

There is not a dependency between the state of playing sports of students and their mothers. %8,5 of the students whose mothers doesn't sport play sport, and %62 of them do.

Table 3: The Crosstabs results of the state of mother's and father's sport condition

The state of playing sports of student			The state of playing sports of father			Total
			Yes	No	Sometimes	
			Yes	N	19	
	%	8,9	60,6	30,5	100,0	
No	N	0	21	11	32	
	%	,0	65,6	34,4	100,0	
Total	N	19	150	76	245	
	%	7,8	61,2	31,0	100,0	

According to table 6, there is no dependency between the sport condition of father and his child. While %8,9 of the students whose fathers are playing sports, %60,6 of them whose fathers aren't playing sports do this activity.

Table 4: The results of the sport activities according to students' sexes

	Male		Female		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Basketball	16	12,5	8	6,8	24	9,8
Football	55	43,0	4	3,4	59	24,1
Volleyball	8	6,3	33	28,2	41	16,7
Athletics	5	3,9	6	5,1	11	4,5
Wrestle	1	0,8	1	0,9	2	0,8
Tennis	4	3,1	5	4,3	9	3,7
Badminton	2	1,6	1	0,9	3	1,2
Handball	2	1,6	3	2,6	5	2,0
Fitness	17	13,3	9	7,7	26	10,6
Other	12	9,4	29	24,8	41	16,7
Not Doing	6	4,7	18	15,4	24	9,8
Total	12	100,0	117	100,0	245	100,0

%43,0 of the male students who take part in the research prefer football, and %0,8 of them prefer wrestle. And %28,2 of the female students prefer volleyball, %0,9 of them prefer wrestle and badminton. Clearly, the wrestle is the least preferred sport for both female and male students.

Table 5: The results of the motivation to do sport according to sexes

		Lose weight	Get rid of being monotonous	Move away from home	Different friends	Gain success	Health	Total
Female	N	32	10	0	4	15	56	117
	%	27,4	8,5	,0	3,4	12,8	47,9	100,0
Male	N	13	14	6	1	29	65	128
	%	10,2	10,9	4,7	,8	22,7	50,8	100,0
Total	N	45	24	6	5	44	121	245
	%	18,4	9,8	2,4	2,0	18,0	49,4	100,0

There is dependency about the reasons of the students to attend the sportive activities in terms of their sexes. %47,9 of the female students take part in sportive activities with the purpose of health, %27,4 of them are for losing weight, and none of them is for moving away from home. And the male students indicate that %50,8 of them do sports for their health, %22,7 are for gaining success, %0,8 of them are for the different friends.

Table 6: The weekly time period of students for sport according to their monthly expenses

		Every other day 1 hour and more	Each day 1 hour and more	Twice a week 1 hour and more	Once a week and 1 hour	Other	Total
100-300 TL	N	0	3	5	5	11	24
	%	,0	12,5	20,8	20,8	45,8	100,0
301-500 TL	N	4	5	15	7	13	44
	%	9,1	11,4	34,1	15,9	29,5	100,0
501-750 TL	N	13	11	19	12	20	75
	%	17,3	14,7	25,3	16,0	26,7	100,0
751-1000 TL	N	13	16	14	3	16	62
	%	21,0	25,8	22,62	4,8	25,8	100,0
More than 1000 TL	N	13	10	8	2	7	40
	%	32,5	25,0	20,0	5,0	17,5	100,0
Total	N	43	45	61	29	67	245
	%	17,6	18,4	24,9	11,8	27,3	100,0

According to table 6, there is a relation between the time they make to sport and their expenses in a month. %32,5 of the students whose monthly expenses are higher than 1000 tl are going to the gym 1 hour or more for every other day, %25,0 of them are going to the gym 1 hour or more for each day. %25,8 of the students whose monthly expenses are between 751-1000 tl prefer to other times, and %25,8 of them prefer to each day for 1 hour or more.

%26,7 of the students whose monthly expenses are between 501-750 tl go to the gym in other times, %25,3 of them do two times in a week and for 1 hour. %34,1 of the students whose monthly expenses are between 301-500 tl go to the gym two times in a week for 1 hour and %45,8 of the ones whose expenses are between 100-300 tl do that in other times. It is clear that most of the students do not sport in certain times or in a planned way and the students who have more opportunities to spend money are going to gym for every other day or each day.

Table 7: The state of playing sports of the students who has a job except their lessons

Students who has a job			The state of playing sports of students		Total
			Yes	No	
	Yes	N		57	4
%			93,4	6,6	100,0
No	N		156	28	184
	%		84,8	15,2	100,0
Total	N		213	32	245
	%		86,9	13,1	100,0

There is a dependency about the state of playing sports and working at a job. %93,4 of the students who have a job are playing sports and %6,6 of them are not. Students who

have a job are more tend to playing sports in comparison with the others. It is a conclusion that students who are not playing sports haven't got any job.

Table 8: The claim of place and purpose of the students to attend the sportive activities

		With Family	With friends	With a new group	Alone	Not Particular	Total
Losing weight	N	2	23	4	11	5	45
	%	4,4	51,1	8,9	24,4	11,1	100,0
Getting rid of being monotonous	N	1	14	1	2	6	24
	%	4,2	58,3	4,2	8,3	25,0	100,0
Moving away from home	N	0	1	0	1	4	6
	%	,0	16,7	,0	16,7	66,7	100,0
Getting a new group of friend	N	0	1	1	2	1	5
	%	,0	20,0	20,0	40,0	20,0	100,0
Gaining success at sport	N	1	20	1	4	18	44
	+	2,3	45,5	2,3	9,1	40,9	100,0
A healthy life	N	1	20	1	4	19	44
	%	3	66	5	8	39	100,0
Total	N	7	125	12	28	73	245
	%	2,9	51,0	4,9	11,4	29,8	100,0

According to table 8, there is dependency between the place and the aims of the students who attend the sportive activities. %51,1 of the students who want to lose weight prefer their group of friends. %58,3 of them prefer their group of friends for not being monotonous, %66,7 of them who want to move away from home say that the place is not important. As %40 they attend alone for getting new friends, %45,5 of the students whose aims are getting success at sport prefer being with friends and %40,9 of them indicate that makes no difference. And the last one, %66 of them prefer the group of friends to be healthy.

Table 9: The results of between the state of playing sport of the students and the sport facilities in their living space

The state of playing sports of students		The state of available sport facilities in their living space		Total
		Yes	No	
Yes	N	158	55	213
	%	74,2	25,8	100,0
No	N	16	16	32
	%	50,0	50,0	100,0
Total	N	174	71	245
	%	71,0	29,0	100,0

There is a dependency between the available sport facilities and the status of playing sports of students. %74,2 of the students whose living space has sport facilities play sports, %25,8 of the part who doesn't have these facilities don't play sports. Half

percentage of the students who don't play sports have sport facilities in their living space, and the rest of them don't have these facilities

4. Conclusion

This research is for determining the level of interest and participation to the sportive recreation activities of the students who study at Trakya University. The first aim is to get the students' demographic information. This aim shows that most of the students attending the research are male, the age range is between 18-23, they study at Kırkpınar Physical Education and Sports and the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, and according to table 4, %80 of them played sport during their childhood.

It is observed that the students whose mothers do not play sport are playing sport more than the others. %8,5 of the students whose mothers play sport are playing, %62 of them whose mothers don't play sport are playing sport. (Table 2) There is not a relation between the status of students and their mothers to play sport. The environmental factors and the developments of sport today can be affective on the students' interests in sport although their mothers don't play sport.

When it is analyzed, the results show that there is not a dependency between the status of playing sport of students and their fathers. %8,9 of the students whose father play sport are playing, %60,6 of them whose fathers don't play sport are playing (Table 3). There is not a relation with the students and the participation to sportive activities of their fathers and mothers. Considering the sexes of the students who participate the research, it is a fact that %28 of the female students prefer volleyball, and %43 of the male students prefer football. (Table 4) As we look at the research, "Determining the Participation Level of College Students to Recreative Activities in Turkey", conducted by Balcı and İlhan (2006) we see that the students study in Akdeniz University show the similarities about the attending to sportive activities.

Their sexes and the reason are related to each other when it comes to sportive activities. So, %49,4 of them attend these activities for their health.

The least aim is to participate for getting new friends in proportion to %2,0. (Table 5) Dr. Yerlisu Lapa and Assoc. Prof. Dr Ardahan compare to the reasons of attending the sportive recreation activities in the way of sex in their study "The Reasons and The Way of Evaluation to Spare Time Activities of The Students in Akdeniz University. With this comparison, they get the information about students prefer to have fun and be with their friends. For this reason, there is a contrast between our studies and theirs. The reason of this contrast is that the students who attend the

sportive recreation activities are more interested in being healthy than the students who attend the spare time activities.

There is not a relation between the time they spare for the sportive activities and their monthly expenses. While %27,4 of the students indicate their participation period of time and there is no particular time to attend, %27 of them indicate that they attend in the other times. Thus, we can make a deduction that regular participation is less than the irregular participation in a week. The students who attend the sportive activities regularly specify their durations with 2 times in a week and 1 hour in the proportion of %24,9. (Table 6) Balcı and İlhan(2006) state that %48,5 of the students attend 2-3 hours in a day and 3-4 days in a week in their study Determining The Participation Level of College Students to Recreative Activities in Turkey and in this respect it is clear that the students from Akdeniz University spare time more than the others.

There is a relation between the status of playing sports of students and working at a job. %93,4 of the students who is working play sports and %6,6 of them don't play. Working is not an obstacle for the students to sport. It can be concluded that the students make time for themselves except their works.

And also there is a relation between the place and the reason. %51,0 of them attend the sportive activities with their group of friends, and the highest reason to attend which is approved by 45 students is losing weight. In the study named The Investigation of the Effect of Changing Health Consciousness on the Level of Participation in Sportive Recreation (Kütahya Case), Köycü Öpözlü (2006) come through that the participants highly prefer to spare time activities in order to be with their friends. While this shows parallelism with the studies, that %31,8 of the participants attend the activities for their health and %10,6 of them attend for losing weight shows that there is a difference between the reasons of their participation. Although the place they attend is not different, that their reasons to participate is different from each other can be based on their nutritional habits.

There is a relation between the state of students' playing sport and the sport facilities in their living spaces. %74,2 of the students who have sport facilities are playing sport and %25,8 of them who don't have sport facilities are playing. So the results show that the status of having sport facilities in their living space affect their participation to sportive activities. (Table 9) A study named Determining the Level of Participation and The Interests of College Youth to Sportive Recreation Activities conducted by Ergül (2008) shows that having sport facilities in living spaces is a enhancing factor of the possibility of playing sports. So we can say that there is not a difference between these studies.

As a conclusion, this study is conducted by looking at the sexes, age range, department, and sportive activities in childhood, parents' condition of the students studying at Kırkpınar Physical Education and Sports and the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences in Trakya University.

We see that the participation of sportive activities is high. Having sport facilities is important for the status of the students' participation to sportive activities. Besides, there are so many students who interested in playing sport during childhood.

There is not a relation between the status of playing sport of parents and the students. The students take part in the sportive activities mostly for losing weight, and according to their monthly expenses, the students who can afford better than the others are more interested in sportive activities, so we think that if the students who cannot afford are provided more social opportunities and resources we can get higher participation in sportive activities.

References

1. Balcı V, Aydın İ, 2006. Türkiye'deki Üniversite Öğrencilerinin Rekreatif etkinliklere Katılım Düzeylerinin Belirlenmesi. SPORMETRE Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi, 2006, IV (1) 11-18.
2. Bayer M.Z, 1992. Turizme Giriş, İstanbul: İşletme Fakültesi Yayınları.
3. Birol S, Karakçük S, 2014. Sportif Rekreasyon Uygulama Politikaları Üzerine Bir Araştırma. KMÜ Sosyal ve Ekonomik Araştırmalar Dergisi 16 (27): 80-86,
4. Ergül O.K, 2008. Üniversite Gençliğinin Sportif Rekreasyon Etkinliklerine Yönelik İlgileri ve Katılma Düzeylerinin Belirlenmesi. Postgraduate Thesis. Celal Bayar Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü.
5. Ekinci S, 1997. Yükseköğretim Gençliğinin Boş Zamanlarını Değerlendirme Alışkanlıkları ve Turizme Katkıları Üzerine Bir Araştırma (Muğla ili örneği). Gazi Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü Yüksek Lisans Tezi.
6. Godbey G, 1999. Leisure In Your Life: An Explonation. II. Edition, Pennsylvania: Venture Publishing Inc.
7. Gökalp H, 2007. Gençliğin Boş Zamanlarını Değerlendirmesinde Spor Faaliyetlerinin Yeri ve Önemi (Tunceli İli örneği). Fırac Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Yüksek Lisans Tezi.
8. Hazar A, 2003. Rekreasyon ve Animasyon, Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık s.25.

9. İç O, 2004. Kamu Görevlilerinin Sportif Rekreasyon Alışkanlıkları ile Rekreasyon Hakkında Görüş ve Beklentilerinin Araştırılması. Karadeniz Technical University, Insitute of Social Sciences Postgraduate Thesis.
10. Karaküçük S, 1995. Rekreasyon, Ankara: Seren Matbaacılık.
11. Karaküçük S, 1999. Rekreasyon (Boş Zaman Değerlendirme), Ankara: Bağırğan Yayınevi.
12. Kaya A, 2011. Üniversite Öğrencilerinin Rekreatif Faaliyetlere Yönelik Turumları ve Boş Zaman Motivasyonlarının Bazı Değişkenler Açısından İncelenmesi. Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimler Enstitüsü, Yüksek Lisans Tezi.
13. Kılbaş S, 2001. Rekreasyon, Adana: Anaca Yayınları s.20.
14. Kılıç K, 2006. Harcanabilir Gelirin Artmasının Sportif Rekreasyona Katılma Olan Etkisinin Araştırılması İstanbul Örneği. Dumlupınar Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Yüksek Lisans Tezi.
15. Kılıç M, Şener G, 2013. Üniversite Öğrencilerinin Rekreasyon Etkinliklerine Katılımlarındaki Sosyolojik Etkenler ve Yapısal Kısıtlamalar. Yükseköğretim ve Bilim Dergisi/Journal of Higher Education and Science DOI: 10.5961/jhes.2013.080
16. Köşker D.Ç, Çimen Z, 2012. Rekreasyonel Spor Hizmetleri Kalite Ölçeği-38'in Türkçe Versiyonu Geçerlilik ve Güvenirlik Çalışması. Niğde Üniversitesi Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi Cilt 6, Sayı 3.
17. Köycü Ö, A, 2006. Çağımızda Değişen Sağlık Bilincinin Sportif Rekreasyona Katılım Düzeyine Etkisinin Araştırılması (Kütahya Örneği). Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Dumlupınar Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
18. Lapa T, Ardahan F, 2009. Akdeniz Üniversitesi Öğrencilerinin Serbest Zaman Etkinliklerine Katılım Nedenleri ve Değerlendirme Biçimleri. Spor Bilimleri Dergisi Hacettepe J. Of Sport sciences 2009, 20 (4),132-144.
19. Lapa T, Ağyar E, 2012. Examination Of Scales In Recreation Area In Turkey. Niğde Üniversitesi Beden Eğitimi Ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi Cilt 6, Sayı 3.
20. Özdilek Ç, Demirel M, Harmandar D, 2007. Dumlupınar ve Sakarya Üniversitelerinde öğrenim gören Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Yüksekokulu öğrencilerinin boş zaman etkinliklerine katılım nedenleri ve düzeylerinin karşılaştırılması. Uluslararası İnsan Bilimleri Dergisi cilt 4, sayı 2.
21. Pepe K, 2008. Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniversitesinde Okuyan Öğrencilerin Serbest Zaman Değerlendirme Anlayış ve Alışkanlıkları İle Beklentilerinin Araştırılması. Spor Yönetimi Ve Bilgi Teknolojileri Dergisi Cilt: 3- Sayı: 1
22. Suiçmez H, 2000. Türkiye ve İngilteredeki Sportif Rekreasyon Yöneticilerinin Karakteristik Özellikleri. Karadeniz Teknik Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Yüksek Lisans Tezi.

23. Şahin İ, Kocabulut, İ. 2014. Sportif Rekreasyon Aktivitelerine Düzenli Katılımı Engelleyen Faktörlerin İncelenmesi Üzerine Bir Araştırma. Journal Of Recreation And Tourism Research (JRTR), 1.
24. Terzioğlu A, Yazıcı M, 2003. Üniversite Öğrencilerinin Boş Zamanlarını Değerlendirme Anlayış ve Alışkanlıkları (Atatürk Üniversitesi Örneği). Erzincan Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi Cilt-Sayı: 5-2
25. Wichasin P, 2007. A Study of Thai Women As Health Tour Participants in Relation To Lifestyle And Leisure Practice, A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of The Requirements of Bournemouth University Fort He Degree of Doctor Of Philosophy.

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